

Complexes of 2-Thienylglyoxal-4'-chloro-1'-iminobenzene with Lanthanum-, Samarium-, Praseodymium-, Neodymium- and Gadolinium(III). Part-II

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A large number of transition metal complexes of multidentate Schiff bases exhibiting a variety of structures have been studied¹. However, relatively small amount of work has been done on the lanthanide complexes² of heterocyclic Schiff bases. Lanthanides owing to nonavailability of orbitals for bonding and large size of their common cations, form few complexes with O or N or S donor ligands³. Hence, in the present investigation such type of Schiff base, 2-thienylglyoxal-4'-chloro-1'-iminobenzene (1) was chosen which contains all the three oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur donor atoms. The Schiff base was obtained by the condensation of 2-thienylglyoxal and *p*-chloroaniline.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were coloured solids having high m.p.s. (>250°). The complexes were found

soluble in DMSO and DMF but insoluble in common organic solvents. Analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes show 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

The molar conductance values 80.7–120.7 Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ of the complexes of La, Pr, Nd, Sm and Gd in DMF indicate 1 : 1 electrolytic nature⁴ and suggest that among the three acetate ions two acetate ions are in coordination with the lanthanide ion. Thus, the complex may be formulated as $[\text{LnL}_2(\text{OAc})_2](\text{OAc})$, where Ln=La, Pr, Sm, Gd and Nd.

Magnetic moment data show that the La complex is diamagnetic while Sm(1.43), Pr(3.51), Nd(3.59) and Gd(7.95 B.M.) complexes are paramagnetic in nature. Magnetic moment values were found to be very close to Van Vleck values⁵ suggesting that 4*f*-electrons of lanthanide ion do not take part in bonding.

Electronic spectral data of the Pr, Nd and Sm complexes alongwith other parameters are given in Table 2. The spectral data have qualitative resemblance with six-coordinated lanthanide complexes⁶.

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complexes	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)					
		C	H	N	S	Cl	Metal
[La(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (CH ₃ COO)	Black	43.52 (44.17)	2.98 (3.06)	3.47 (3.43)	7.95 (7.85)	8.42 (8.71)	16.90 (17.04)
[Pr(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (CH ₃ COO)	Black	43.81 (44.06)	3.00 (3.06)	3.17 (3.42)	7.99 (7.83)	8.42 (8.69)	17.02 (17.24)
[Nd(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (CH ₃ COO)	Brown	43.01 (43.88)	3.10 (3.04)	3.28 (3.41)	7.63 (7.80)	8.69 (8.65)	17.31 (17.58)
[Sm(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (CH ₃ COO)	Brown	43.21 (43.56)	2.82 (3.02)	3.11 (3.38)	7.92 (7.74)	8.62 (8.59)	17.81 (18.19)
[Gd(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (CH ₃ COO)	Black	42.81 (43.20)	2.88 (3.00)	3.16 (3.36)	7.72 (7.68)	8.42 (8.52)	18.67 (18.87)

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF Nd, Pr AND Sm COMPLEXES

NdCl ₃ *	[Nd(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO)	β	$(1-\beta)$ $\times 10^{-2}$	$b^{\frac{1}{2}}$	δ %	η	Assignment
12 500	12 370	0.989 6	1.04	0.072 1	1.05	0.005 2	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}
13 330	13 240	0.993 2	0.68	0.058 3	0.68	0.003 4	→ ⁴ F _{1/2}
14 700	14 580	0.991 8	0.82	0.064 0	0.83	0.004 1	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}
17 240	17 090	0.991 3	0.87	0.064 4	0.88	0.004 4	→ (⁴ G _{5/2} , ³ G _{7/2})
19 410	19 320	0.995 4	0.46	0.048 0	0.46	0.002 3	→ ⁴ G _{3/2}
21 730	21 590	0.993 6	0.64	0.056 6	0.64	0.003 2	→ ⁴ G _{11/2}
PrCl ₃ *	[Pr(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO)						
16 949	16 667	0.983 3	1.66	0.091 1	1.68	0.008 4	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂
20 833	20 618	0.989 6	1.03	0.071 8	1.04	0.005 2	→ ³ P ₀
22 472	22 222	0.988 8	1.11	0.074 5	1.12	0.005 6	→ ³ P ₂
SmCl ₃ *	[Sm(C ₁₂ H ₈ NSOCl) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO)						
21 500	21 280	0.989 7	1.02	0.071 4	1.03	0.005 2	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ G _{5/2}
24 090	23 920	0.992 9	0.71	0.059 6	0.72	0.003 6	→ ⁴ I _{5/2}
25 000	24 940	0.997 6	0.24	0.034 6	0.24	0.001 2	→ ⁶ P _{3/2}

*In H₂O.

The nephelauxetic effect (β) which is a measure of covalency in the metal ligand bond, and other parameters like covalency factor ($b^{\frac{1}{2}}$), angular overlap parameter (η) and Sinha parameter ($\delta\%$) were calculated⁷. Positive and very low values of $b^{\frac{1}{2}}$ indicates poor covalency of the complexes. Low values of $\delta\%$ also suggests weak covalent bonding as well as weak metal-ligand interaction.

The Schiff base has three potential coordination sites, viz. thiophene sulphur, carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. Infrared spectral data show that the Schiff base acts as a bidentate ligand and is coordinated to metal ion through its carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen only. In the infrared spectra of Schiff base, a medium intensity band appeared at 1 230–1 240 cm⁻¹ which does not show any marked shift in the spectra of the complexes indicating that C—S—C frequency is not so sensitive to the complexation and sulphur of thiophene ring does not take part in bond formation⁸. All the lanthanide complexes showed a decrease by 60–95 and 20–35 cm⁻¹ in $\nu_{C=O}$ (1 760) and $\nu_{C=N}$ (1 680 cm⁻¹) bands respectively of the free

ligand, thereby showing the coordination of both carbonyl oxygen⁹ and azomethine nitrogen¹⁰ to the lanthanide ion, which was further supported by the appearance of two new bands in the regions 440–480 cm⁻¹ and 380–390 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{Ln-O} and ν_{Ln-N} stretching modes¹¹ respectively. Coordination of acetate ion was supported by the appearance of two bands at 1 595–1 490 and 1 365–1 350 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ and $\nu_s(COO^-)$ modes respectively of metal-acetate bond¹².

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Lanthanide chlorides (99.99% purity; Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and 4-chloroaniline (B.D.H.) were used. 2-Acetylthiophene and its glyoxal were prepared by making slight modifications in the original method¹³. 2-Thierylglyoxal-4'-chloro-1'-iminobenzene (TGCIB) was prepared according to the literature method¹⁴.

Synthesis of complexes: All lanthanide chlorides were first converted into lanthanide acetate by dissolving in ethanol and treating them with ethanolic solution of sodium acetate in equimolar ratio.

Precipitated sodium chloride was separated by filtration. To the lanthanide acetate solution was added ethanolic solution of the Schiff base. All the complexes precipitated immediately after mixing these two solutions, which were washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol then with ether and dried over fused CaCl_2 .

Metal contents were estimated by complexometric titration with EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator. Sulphur was estimated by standard method¹⁵. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated on Thomas CH analyser and Coleman N-analyser. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on Gouy's balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant at 300 K. Conductance was measured using their 10^{-5} M solutions in DMF using a Systronic 303 conductometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in liquid state on a Spectronic 20D spectrophotometer and infrared spectra (CsI) on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer.

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